

SUPERNOVA

D7.4 / Tracking of KPIs – First Version

WP 7, T7.4

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Technical references

Project Acronym	SUPERNOVA
Project Title	Operation and Maintenance and Grid Friendly Tools and Solutions for Solar Data Fusion and Insight Explosion for Reliable, Bankable, Circular PV Plants
Project Coordinator	Lukas Koester Eurac Research Lukas.koester@eurac.edu
Project Duration	April 2024 – September 2027 (42 months)
Deliverable No.	D7.4
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 7 – Profitability and Exploitation
Task	T7.4 – Innovation and Impact Verification of KPIs
Lead beneficiary	Eurac Research (EURAC)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	STATKRAFT
Due date of deliverable	31 May 2025 (M14)
Actual submission date	31 May 2025

- *PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project’s page)
- SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

v	Date	Beneficiary	Author
1.0	30/05/2025	Eurac Research	Lukas Koester

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1. Executive Summary

The SUPERNOVA project improves quality and efficiency along the whole value chain by breaking silos between all involved stakeholders. In this document the key performance indicators (KPIs) related to innovation in the SUPERNOVA project are mapped and monitored. It provides a structured approach for assessing how the project's innovative activities contribute to measurable outcomes.

The SUPERNOVA project focuses on enhancing grid-friendliness by optimizing PV plant designs to improve operational efficiency and resilience against weather challenges. These developments are designed to be measurable and directly tied to the project's performance benchmarks.

Robotic technologies, such as drones and field robots equipped with advanced inspection sensors, are being integrated to streamline maintenance processes, cut costs, and improve fault detection capabilities. These innovations are aligned with specific KPIs for operational performance.

Data collection is improved by developing smart modules and IoT-enabled devices providing high-resolution monitoring and failure detection. These tools aim to deliver quantifiable improvements in data accuracy and system reliability.

Effective data management is critical, and SUPERNOVA focuses on analyzing and integrating O&M data across stakeholders to ensure consistency and actionable insights. AI-driven solutions are being developed to simplify analysis and enhance operational decision-making.

Profitability improvements are achieved by creating innovative business models for data monetization and refining energy trading practices. These strategies contribute to measurable economic benefits for the PV sector.

SUPERNOVA also emphasizes secure and efficient data sharing. The creation of a tailored energy data space for the PV sector facilitates customized sharing while supporting additional applications for data processing. This initiative is designed to address privacy concerns and improve collaboration, forming the basis for tracking progress against established KPIs.

This document connects closely with the Plan for Exploitation of Results (PER) drafted in T7.3, offering a more detailed look at the numerical data driving the project's advancements. While the PER focuses on tracking overall outcomes, this report provides specific metrics to give a clearer picture of the impact of SUPERNOVA's work.

The initial version is drafted in month (M) 14 of the project duration and will be updated in M28 and finalized by the end of the project in M42. By updating the KPIs throughout the project, this process allows for ongoing monitoring and adjustments, ensuring that the project stays on track and meets its benchmarks.

Ultimately, this report aims to support the management of SUPERNOVA's innovations by providing clear, actionable data and keeping progress aligned with the project's measurable goals. It is a practical tool for ensuring accountability and informed decision-making over the course of the project's duration.

2. Definitions and acronyms

CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
CPN	Cost Priority Number
EU	European Union
IRR	Internal Rate of Return
KPI	Key performance index
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Electricity
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
O&M	Operation and maintenance
PER	Plan for exploitation of Results
PR	Performance ratio
WACC	Weighted Average Cost of Capital

3. Methodology

The KPI mapping works by drafting for each KPI a table containing a description, the target value and fields to update throughout the project.

The KPI mapping process begins by referencing the objectives outlined in the project proposal. These are divided into KPIs of specific results, which are direct improvements measurable due to project results (cf. Table 1), and global KPIs describing which impact the specific contributions of SUPERNOVA (also the specific results) have on a global scale on the PV sector (cf. Table 2). While the specific results will be visible and therefore evaluated already during the project, the latter will only start to become visible after the projects lifetime; first improvements are expected in the year after the project ends. Therefore, the global KPIs must be calculated/estimated using the KPIs measured for the specific project results.

The target value for the specific results KPIs is set for the end of the project, although some of SUPERNOVA's developments and innovations might need final integration even beyond the project lifetime to become fully evident. They will be monitored throughout the project's duration, with significant progress typically becoming evident during the second review phase.

The evaluation methods for KPIs vary based on their nature. Some KPIs can be assessed directly, as their benefits are immediately measurable or observable. Others require additional calculations, information, or assumptions to determine their impact. This iterative process ensures that the KPI mapping document remains up-to-date and reflective of ongoing developments within the project.

For each specific result, the corresponding KPIs are tracked in a table that includes the KPI identifier, a description, and the projected improvements expected at different stages of the project. This approach offers clarity and enables consistent tracking of progress toward achieving the project's goals.

Table 1: KPIs of specific results, to be reached by 2030 as outlined in the SUPERNOVA project proposal.

Specific results	Impacted KPIs	Target Value
Grid friendly design	Curtailement / hosting capacity / unavailability / IRR	-15% / +50% / -1% / +3%
O&M friendly design	Yield assessment uncertainty / O&M cost / IRR / Performance Loss rate	<5% / -5% / +5% / -0.5%
Smart module	Yield	+3%
Spectroscopy based condition monitoring	Remaining Useful Lifetime estimation	Increased accuracy
DC harnessing enabling automatic PL	Yield / Time to detection / CPN / Inspected PV plant throughput	+1% / -50% / -2 €/kWp/y / 20 MW/day
Smart control for trackers	Downtime / CAPEX	-70% / -25% cabling
Next generation in field-robotics	Time to detection / Yield / O&M cost / Unavailability	-25% / +1% / -5% / -1%
Hybridised field and aerial robotic solutions	Time to detection / Yield / O&M cost / Inspected and analysed PV plant	-50% / +1% / -5% / 6 MW/h
Computer vision based O&M tools	O&M cost	-15%
Second life and re-use of components	% repair/reuse after EoL of first life PV / Cumulative lifetime	>50% / 40 years
ITLLM based Asset management platform	O&M cost	-20%
Scalable, digital twin intelligent platform	Soft cost reduction	-20%
Energy trading	MAE cost	-15%
Innovative Approaches for PV and Storage	Curtailement reduction	-15%
Energy Space	Amount of data	100 GW / 10000 images

Table 2: Expected KPIs following concrete results of the SUPERNOVA project as outlined in the project proposal. As these KPIs are related to improvements that are expected on a global scale, their impact will start becoming effective only the year after the end of the project.

Expected impact	How SUPERNOVA addressed the impact (Target 2029)	
Increase utility-friendly integration of PV generation at high penetration levels	Curtailment reduction: 15% / Hosting capacity increase: 50% in the distribution grid, 100% in transmission grid thanks to PV as programmable unit	
Increase performance of PV systems	Cost priority number of PV system (total cost of O&M, insurance, warranties, etc) < 10 Euro/kWp/y / Performance Ratio > 90% / Proven Useful Lifetime of PV modules > 40 years	
Increase profitability of PV systems	WACC reduction: 1% / O&M costs reduction: 50% / LCOE reduction between 30-50%, IRR increase of +5% absolute with a PPA of 60 Euros/MWh thanks to PR increase, decrease in PLR, decrease in O&M costs. / IRR increase +3% absolute with optimized used of storage + proactive curtailment + smart control + forecasting in energy trading	
Other impacts	Target 2029	Target 2035
Economic benefits	1.4 million € for SUPERNOVA partners	850 million of € per year
Jobs created by the project		10,000 jobs / year
Stakeholders participating in trainings and workshops	3,000 (SUPERNOVA will cohost the SPE's Solar Quality Summit)	
Stakeholders reached through media and events	150,000	
Data collected in the PV Data Space	100 GW worth of timeseries data / 10000 images from multispectral analysis by 2030 / 1000 verified high quality time series / 1000 images openly available for R&D by 2030 / 30 companies beyond the consortium as data deliverers	
SUPERNOVA reduces the technical and financial risks by developing methodologies to assess the economic impact of failures in the field / by developing mitigation measures towards severe weather events and preventive and data-driven corrective mitigation measures, thus decreasing the risk profile of PV projects to give confidence to investors and lenders and thus enabling lower WACCs. Targeted -1% in WACC.		
SUPERNOVA contributes to the enhancement of the competitiveness of the EU PV industry and comply with EU policies to increase the share of renewable energy sources.		
SUPERNOVA increases the innovation capacity of SMEs and contributes to the creation of added value services that can be delivered by SMEs in the field of downstream services for the PV sector		
SUPERNOVA overcomes non-technical barriers that prevent investors and stakeholders from increasing the share of renewable energy generation		

4. KPI Mapping

4.1. KPIs of Specific Results

4.1.1. Grid friendly design

Designing PV plants to be grid-friendly means ensuring they can operate reliably and flexibly within existing grid constraints while supporting overall system stability. SUPERNOVA addresses this by integrating advanced forecasting, adaptive control strategies, and digital monitoring tools. These innovations help reduce energy losses, improve responsiveness to grid signals, and lower downtime. As a result, key technical and economic KPIs such as curtailment, hosting capacity, unavailability, and IRR are expected to improve significantly. These developments are mainly done in WP2 and WP5.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target value	M28 update	M42 final update
Curtailment	The share of available PV energy that cannot be fed into the grid. SUPERNOVA minimizes curtailment through better forecasting and grid-adaptive plant operation.	-15%		
Hosting capacity	Hosting capacity is the maximum amount of distributed PV generation that can be connected to a specific part of the electricity grid without negatively impacting grid stability or requiring costly upgrades. It reflects the grid's ability to integrate renewable energy while maintaining power quality and reliability.	+50%		
Unavailability	Unavailability measures the proportion of time the PV system is unable to generate or deliver electricity due to faults, maintenance, or grid issues. SUPERNOVA reduces unavailability by leveraging automated fault detection, predictive maintenance using sensor data, and robotic inspection technologies.	-1%		
IRR	Internal Rate of Return (IRR) is a financial metric that represents the expected annual return on investment over the system's lifetime. By minimizing energy losses, reducing downtime, and improving grid compatibility, SUPERNOVA contributes to a more stable and profitable revenue stream, leading to an increase in IRR.	+3%		

4.1.2. Operation and maintenance (O&M) friendly design

Designing PV plants with operation and maintenance (O&M) in mind helps ensure long-term performance, lower lifecycle costs, and higher reliability. SUPERNOVA addresses this by integrating smart monitoring systems, robotic inspection tools, AI-driven diagnostics, and

predictive maintenance strategies. These innovations reduce manual labor, improve fault detection accuracy, and allow for more precise yield estimation. The result is a more efficient O&M process, leading to better technical performance and improved financial returns.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target value	M28 update	M42 final update
Yield assessment uncertainty	This refers to the margin of error in predicting the expected energy output of a PV system. SUPERNOVA reduces this uncertainty by combining real-world performance data with advanced modeling and monitoring, resulting in more accurate and reliable yield forecasts.	<5%		
O&M costs	These are the operational expenses related to inspection, maintenance, and repairs over the system’s lifetime. SUPERNOVA lowers O&M costs through automation, predictive analytics, and the use of robotic systems, which reduce the need for manual inspections and reactive maintenance.	-5%		
IRR	IRR reflects the overall profitability of the PV investment. By cutting O&M costs and increasing reliability and uptime, SUPERNOVA enhances the economic efficiency of PV systems, leading to improved IRR.	+5%		
Performance loss rate	This KPI measures the annual degradation or reduction in a PV system’s energy output. SUPERNOVA minimizes performance losses through early fault detection, continuous monitoring, and data-driven maintenance that addresses issues before they impact long-term performance.	-0.5%		

4.1.3. Smart Module

Smart modules integrate additional functionalities—such as embedded sensors, module-level monitoring, and optimization electronics—directly into the PV module. These features enable more granular performance tracking, better fault detection, and improved energy harvesting under different conditions. Within SUPERNOVA, smart modules are developed and tested to enhance both energy output and system reliability by providing real-time insights and enabling local optimization.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target value	M28 update	M42 final update
Yield	The actual amount of energy produced by the PV system over a given period, normalized by installed capacity (e.g. kWh/kWp). It reflects the system’s effectiveness in converting sunlight into usable electricity.	+3%		

4.1.4. Spectroscopy based condition monitoring

Spectroscopy-based condition monitoring uses optical techniques to analyze the physical and chemical state of PV modules non-destructively. By capturing spectral signatures related to degradation or material changes, this approach allows for early fault detection, precise ageing assessment, and data-driven maintenance planning. In SUPERNOVA, these methods are developed and integrated into prototype tools for real-time, in-field diagnostics that enhance long-term reliability and reduce operational risks.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target value	M28 update	M42 final update
Remaining useful lifetime estimation	The predicted duration a PV module or component can continue to perform within expected parameters before it reaches end-of-life or requires replacement.	Increased accuracy		
Spectroscopy prototypes	The number and development stage of functional spectroscopy-based tools created to assess PV module condition, enabling on-site, non-invasive diagnostics and estimation of power degradation.	2 prototypes		

4.1.5. DC harnessing enabling automatic PL

DC harnessing solutions that enable automated photoluminescence (PL) imaging allow for non-contact, high-resolution inspection of PV modules under natural illumination conditions. By integrating PL capabilities directly into the DC wiring and inverters, the system can capture performance-related defects without shutting down the plant or interrupting power production. In SUPERNOVA, this approach is developed to enable continuous, scalable diagnostics at string or module level, ultimately supporting higher yields, faster fault detection, and improved plant throughput.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target value	M28 update	M42 final update
Yield	The total energy produced per installed capacity (kWh/kWp) over time. Automatic PL helps identify underperforming modules quickly, allowing for corrective actions that recover lost yield and maintain optimal energy output.	+1%		
Time detection	The duration between the origin of a fault and its identification. Automatic PL significantly reduces time to detection by continuously monitoring for defects without the need for manual inspection or shutdowns. This will be reached by combination with developments in robotic solutions.	-50%		
CPN	The Cost Priority Number (CPN) is a risk-based metric combining the cost, severity, and likelihood of a fault to prioritize maintenance actions. Automatic PL provides timely and detailed fault	-2€/kWp/y		

	data, enabling accurate CPN assessments and smarter maintenance prioritization.			
Inspected PV plant throughput	The installed PV capacity that can be inspected per unit time. Automatic PL enables scalable, rapid inspections across large plants, greatly increasing throughput compared to manual methods.	20MW/day		

4.1.6. Smart control for trackers

Smart control of PV trackers employs advanced algorithms and sensor data to optimize panel orientation for maximum energy capture while minimizing mechanical stress. SUPERNOVA adopts a dedicated design approach for tracker system protection against hostile climatic and meteorological events—such as strong winds, heavy snow, hail, and sandstorms—to reduce and mitigate the risks of tracker failures and breakdowns caused by these severe conditions. This combination of smart control and robust design enhances reliability, lowers maintenance needs, and improves overall plant efficiency.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target value	M28 update	M42 final update
Downtime	The period when trackers are non-operational due to faults or maintenance. Smart control reduces downtime by enabling predictive maintenance and smoother operations.	-70%		
CAPEX	Capital expenditures (CAPEX) related to installing and commissioning trackers. Optimized control can lower CAPEX by reducing mechanical wear and extending tracker lifespan, delaying costly replacements.	-25% cabling		
Production	The total energy generated by the PV system. Improved tracker positioning and reduced downtime directly increase production efficiency. (field simulation tests and numerical simulations)	+5%		

4.1.7. Next generation in-field robotics

Next generation in-field robotics combines advanced autonomous platforms equipped with multiple sensors and tools to perform comprehensive inspections, maintenance, and cleaning of PV plants. SUPERNOVA focuses on developing versatile robotic solutions capable of delivering multiple services from a single platform, increasing operational efficiency and reducing human intervention. These innovations enable faster fault detection, proactive maintenance, and lower downtime, ultimately improving plant performance and reducing costs.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target value	M28 update	M42 final update
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Time detection to	The interval between the onset of a fault and its identification. Robotic solutions accelerate detection by enabling continuous, automated inspection without manual effort.	-25%		
Yield	The actual energy output of the PV system. Faster fault detection and maintenance by robots help recover lost production and maintain higher yield.	+1%		
O&M cost	Operational expenses related to maintenance activities. Combining multiple services on one robotic platform lowers O&M costs by reducing labor and inspection time.	-5%		
Unavailability	The time during which the plant or parts of it are offline due to faults or maintenance. Autonomous robotics reduce unavailability by speeding up inspections and repairs.	-1%		
Cost of robotic solutions	The total investment and operating costs of robotic platforms. SUPERNOVA optimizes cost-efficiency by integrating several maintenance and inspection functions into a single robot, minimizing overall expenses.	5€/kWp/y		

4.1.8. Hybridised field and aerial robotic solutions

Hybridised robotic solutions combine ground-based and aerial platforms to provide comprehensive, flexible, and efficient inspection and maintenance of PV plants. SUPERNOVA develops integrated systems that leverage the strengths of both robotic types—ground robots for detailed close-up inspections and aerial drones for rapid large-area surveys. This hybrid approach improves coverage, reduces inspection times, and enhances data quality, supporting better maintenance decisions and plant performance.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target value	M28 update	M42 (2027) final update
Time detection to	The duration from fault occurrence to identification. The combined use of field and aerial robots speeds up fault detection by enabling continuous and complementary inspections.	-50%		
Yield	The total energy generated by the PV plant. Early detection and resolution of faults through hybrid robotic monitoring help maintain or improve yield.	+1%		
O&M cost	Expenses related to inspection and maintenance activities. Hybrid robotics reduce O&M costs by optimizing inspection efficiency and minimizing manual labor.	-5%		
Inspected and analysed PV plant	The installed PV capacity that can be inspected and analyzed within a certain time. Hybrid systems increase throughput by covering larger areas	6 MW/h		

	quickly with drones and detailed inspections with ground robots.			
Processes	The hybridization of field and aerial robotic solutions will have an impact on above described KPIs. To keep O&M costs manageable when using robotic solutions, these have to be fully automated. This KPI gives the number of processes to be improved by hybridization.	5 processes		

4.1.9. Computer vision based O&M tools

Computer vision–based tools use advanced image processing and machine learning algorithms to automate the detection, classification, and diagnosis of PV system faults from visual data. SUPERNOVA develops and integrates these tools to enhance inspection accuracy, reduce manual workload, and support augmented reality (AR) applications for field technicians, thereby improving maintenance efficiency and decision-making.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target value	M28 update	M42 final update
O&M costs	Operational and maintenance expenses reduced through automation of visual inspections, better image analysis and faster fault identification enabled by computer vision.	-15%		
AR products	Augmented reality (AR) solutions to assist technicians during in-field operation procedures in the PV sector.	2		
Image analysis algorithms	New algorithms in image analysis to correlate image to power loss. Shown in scientific publications.	4 new algorithms		

4.1.10. Second life and re-use of components

Extending the life of PV components through repair, refurbishment, and repurposing supports circular economy principles and reduces environmental impact. SUPERNOVA explores strategies and technologies to enable reliable second-life applications of PV modules and system parts, increasing resource efficiency and reducing waste.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target value	M28 update	M42 final update
% repair/reuse after EoL of first life PV	The proportion of components that are successfully repaired or repurposed for a second operational life after reaching the end of their first service period.	>50%		
Cumulative lifetime	The total operational time that PV components provide across both their first and second life	40 years		

cycles, reflecting improved resource utilization and sustainability.

4.1.11. ITLLM based Asset management platform

The Instruction Tuned Large Language Models (ITLLM) based asset management platform utilizes advanced natural language processing and AI to interpret complex operational data, automate decision-making, and enhance communication within PV plant management. SUPERNOVA integrates ITLLMs to improve predictive maintenance, fault diagnostics, and operational workflows, reducing downtime and optimizing costs.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target value	M28 update	M42 final update
O&M cost	Cost reduction due to the asset management platform, to be proven for selected processes.	-20%		
AI solutions	New services based on AI language-based solutions. To be shown as beta-releases in partners' digital platforms. 2 of these should show fully automated processes without the need of human intervention from unwanted operating conditions detection to detailed forensic to suggested course of action. This process has to be documented.	4 services		

4.1.12. Scalable, digital twin intelligent platform

A scalable digital twin platform creates a virtual replica of the PV plant, integrating real-time data, simulations, and AI analytics to support operational decisions and predictive maintenance. SUPERNOVA develops this platform to avoid information loss along the value chain by enabling a comprehensive, digital twin-based PV portfolio intelligence system. This approach enhances plant management through detailed scenario analysis, faster troubleshooting, and improved planning, streamlining workflows and reducing operational complexities.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target value	M28 update	M42 final update
Soft cost reduction	The decrease in indirect costs such as administrative overhead, project management, and inspection expenses. The digital twin platform reduces these soft costs by automating data analysis, improving coordination, and minimizing manual interventions.	-20%		

4.1.13. Energy trading

SUPERNOVA supports advanced forecasting and market participation strategies to enhance the competitiveness of PV systems in energy markets. By integrating predictive models and real-time data into trading algorithms, the project aims to improve forecast accuracy and optimize bidding strategies, reducing financial risks.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target value	M28 update	M42 final update
MAE cost	Mean absolute error (MAE) during forecasting as tool for energy trading. The costs due to the error will be reduced by improved forecasting tools developed in WP5.	-15%		

4.1.14. Innovative Approaches for PV and Storage

SUPERNOVA explores the integration of innovative PV system designs with energy storage solutions to enhance flexibility, grid compatibility, and energy availability. By enabling better load balancing and peak shaving, these approaches help maximize energy use and reduce reliance on curtailment during grid congestion.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target value	M28 update	M42 final update
Curtailment reduction	The decrease in energy production losses due to grid limitations or oversupply. Combining PV with storage enables energy shifting and better grid interaction, thereby reducing curtailment events.	-15%		

4.1.15. Energy Data Space

SUPERNOVA contributes to the development of a shared, interoperable data space to enable efficient data exchange across the PV value chain. By fostering standardization and collaboration, the project supports better integration of time series, image-based, and contextual data, while exploring sustainable business models for long-term accessibility and value generation.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target value	M28 update	M42 final update
Timeseries data	The quantity and quality of operational and performance-related timeseries data collected and made available within the data space.	100 GW		
Images	The volume of image-based datasets (e.g. infrared, PL, EL, RGB) collected and stored in the data space for analysis and AI development.	10,000 images		

Openly available date	The portion of collected timeseries and image data that is openly accessible to the public, supporting research and development and thus broader innovation, as well as transparency.	1000 images		
Participating companies	The number of companies (beyond the consortium) actively contributing to or using the data space, indicating stakeholder engagement and ecosystem growth.	30 companies		
Business model	New business model based on data monetization (to be validated with external stakeholders).	One		

4.2. Global KPIs

The tables below summarize how the concrete Results of SUPERNOVA contribute globally to the different expected impacts for the utility scale sector. Most of SUPERNOVA’s innovations will also benefit other market segments (rooftop, agri-PV, etc). We assume these impacts will start becoming effective the year after the end of the project, in 2029. Their calculation follows in the second part of this section.

4.2.1. Increase utility-friendly integration of PV generation at high penetration levels

As PV deployment scales up, ensuring that large volumes of solar energy can be reliably integrated into the grid becomes essential. SUPERNOVA supports this goal by developing technologies and strategies—such as advanced inverters, storage integration, smart controls, and grid-supportive designs—to enable stable operation and reduce the impact of PV variability on the electricity system.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target 2029	Target 2035	M28 update	M42 (2027) final update
Curtailment	The reduction of PV output due to grid limitations. Improving grid compatibility and flexibility to minimize energy losses from curtailment even at high penetration levels.	-15%	N/A		
Hosting capacity	The maximum amount of PV that can be connected to a grid segment without requiring reinforcements or compromising stability. Hosting capacity is increased by treating PV systems as programmable units—capable of responding dynamically to grid signals—thereby enhancing controllability, flexibility, and grid support capabilities.	+50% in Distribution grid, +100% in transmission grid	N/A		

4.2.2. Increase performance of PV systems

Improving the performance of PV systems is essential for lowering the cost of solar electricity and maximizing long-term value. SUPERNOVA enhances system performance through advanced materials, intelligent design, improved diagnostics, and predictive maintenance—all aimed at increasing energy output, reducing failures, and extending system lifetime.

Impacted KPI	Description	Target 2029	Target 2035	M28 update	M42 (2027) final update
CPN of PV system	The Cost Priority Number combines the severity, occurrence, and detectability of system failures into a risk-based cost metric. SUPERNOVA reduces the CPN by deploying predictive diagnostics and robust design measures to minimize costly system faults.	<10€/kWp/y	N/A		
PR	Performance ratio (PR) is the ratio between actual and theoretical energy output, indicating overall system efficiency. We raise PR through improved component quality, advanced monitoring, and intelligent O&M strategies.	>90%	N/A		
Proven Useful Lifetime of PV modules	The demonstrated operational duration of PV modules under real-world conditions. SUPERNOVA aims to extend this lifetime through better materials, early degradation detection, and optimized system operation.	>40 years	N/A		

4.2.3. Increase profitability of PV systems

Impacted KPI	Description	Target 2029	Target 2035	M28 update	M42 (2027) final update
WACC	Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC) is the average rate of return a company or project is expected to pay to its investors (equity + debt holders) for using their capital. It reflects the opportunity cost of investing money in a specific project rather than elsewhere. SUPERNOVA reduces technical and financial risks by developing methodologies to assess the economic impact of failures in the field / by developing mitigation measures towards severe weather events and preventive and data-driven corrective mitigation measures, thus decreasing the risk profile of PV projects to give confidence to investors and lenders and thus enabling lower WACCs.	-1%	N/A		

O&M cost	The ongoing expenses related to operating and maintaining PV systems. There will be reduced O&M costs via automation, predictive maintenance, and AI-driven diagnostics.	- 50%	N/A		
LCOE	Levelized cost of Electricity (LCOE) average cost per unit of electricity (usually €/MWh or \$/kWh) over the lifetime of the system	- 30-50%	N/A		
IRR	5% absolute increase with a power purchase agreement (PPA) of 60 €/MWh. This is achieved due to increase in PR, decrease in PLR, decrease in O&M costs. 3% absolute increase with optimized use of storage, proactive curtailment, smart control, and forecasting in energy trading.	+ 5%			

Explanation how these values are calculated:

We pursue an overall reduction of costs for O&M by 50%, i.e., from 10 €/kWp to 5 €/kWp per year in new PV plants using SUPERNOVA solutions. In terms of OPEX as seen by the investor and relevant stakeholders (module warranty, insurance claims/premiums, soft costs), this translates to a cost reduction of 67%, i.e., from 30 €/kWp to 10 €/kWp per year for large commercial to utility scale PV plants. This is achieved by:

- (i) reduced uncertainty on the yield assessment thanks to inclusion of mitigation of severe weather and O&M friendly design, consequently, increase in yield in the business model due to higher P90 values,
- (ii) higher knowledge on component quality, consequently, reduction of number of failures, their economic impact in terms of unavailability (increase in yield) and cost for substitution/repair, optimized tracking and smart control
- (iii) higher automation of the operations process through advanced monitoring and automated field inspection, consequently, reduction of time to detection and repair,
- (iv) more targeted maintenance by moving from periodic to reactive or predictive maintenance for fault avoidance or early fault detection and automation of process workflow. These impacts together with reduced Performance Loss Rates (from 0.8% to 0.25%), increase in project lifetime (25y to 40y), and increase in PR (from 0.8 to 0.9) could lead to an overall LCOE decrease of up to 50% (Figure 6, EURAC elaboration) and an increase of IRR of more than 50% relative.

One year after the end of the project in 2029 the partners will have implemented SUPERNOVA Results on a portfolio of at least 50 MWp of new projects with a benefit of 400 k€/y in increase yield (considering a PPA of 60 €/MWh and 10% increase in yield) and a reduction in OPEX costs of 67% for an estimated saving of 1 M€ per annum (considering 20 €/kWp in reduction). SUPERNOVA is expected to generate savings and extra income for the partners of the order of 1.4 million €/year in 2029 with an investment of 2.5 million €, thus with a return of investment in less than 2 years. The utility market segment in EU accounts for 34% of the cumulative PV capacity by 2022. A direct linear extrapolation (using the Low Scenario from the SPE EU Market Outlook) would lead to around 200 GW capacity by 2030. It is rather difficult to estimate what the electricity valorization will be in 2030-2035 using PPAs. Initial large decrease in EU PPAs was due to market assessment and a fast learning rate in bidding for utility scale tenders. If we assume a 50% decrease in the next 10

years we could see PPAs of around 25 €/MWh in Europe. Non optimized assets in terms of yield could lead in 2030 to production loss of around 14 TWh (5% of an annual generation of 200 GW with a yield of 1400 kWh/kWp as per baseline), 350 million of €/year. By 2035 SUPERNOVA solutions will become state of the art leading to a reduction in losses equal to 65% in existing plants and up to 82% in new plants, at least 200 million of € in avoided losses/year. The increase in at least 5% in yield thanks to more accurate yield prediction and design would generate extra income equal to around 50 million of € in new utility scale PV plants (60 GW per annum in 2030). To consider the reduction in OPEX, we would need to extrapolate a value for 2035. Using a 67% reduction from the baseline value (30 €/kWp) and keeping the 2030 SUPERNOVA target value (10 €/kWp), the estimated savings would amount to 600 million € in new utility scale PV plants. Based on the given assumptions, the overall benefit in conservative terms for 2035 for the utility scale sector in terms of more generation in the EU could be then estimated at 850 million € per year.

5. Next Steps and Future Updates

This document serves as a living draft to support the continuous collection, organization, and preliminary assessment of SUPERNOVA's project-level KPIs. As the project evolves, these KPIs will be continuously reviewed, and improved where necessary, to ensure that they remain relevant, measurable, and aligned with the actual developments and outputs of the project.

Public updates of this deliverable are planned as follows:

- **Month 28:** Publication of an updated KPI report incorporating the first full assessment cycle, including data from demonstrators, simulations, and/or use-case pilots.
- **Month 42:** Submission of the final KPI assessment, summarizing the overall impact achieved and lessons learned.

Internally, this document will be updated continuously, as project results and data become available. Partners are encouraged to contribute to the refinement and validation of KPIs through their ongoing work. Feedback and insights from stakeholders, including end users and external advisors, will also be incorporated where relevant.

This iterative approach ensures that the KPI tracking remains responsive to the project's innovations and provides an accurate, evidence-based evaluation of its progress and impact.

